

Review report on extended abstract titled “From reuse to impact: monitoring data reuse in CESSDA archives”

Authors (alphabetically by last name)

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Feedback Reviewer 1 Janne Polonen

ID	Reviewer 1				
	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID11	5	4	3	4	Accept

This poster presents an original procedure and script for tracking the reuse of research data in CESSDA archives by using DOIs to identify citations in scholarly literature indexed in the Scopus database. A poster focused on data citations is highly relevant to the conference theme "Recognition of contributions to Open Science." It also aims to demonstrate ways to overcome certain technical and practical limitations in measuring data reuse. While these limitations are not fully specified in the abstract (possibly because of the limited space), the paper previously mentions, for example, "the absence of optimal citation practices."

The study appears to propose a potentially significant contribution to the challenge of tracking data citations, although I am not able to fully assess its novelty, as data citation is not my area of expertise. Nonetheless, the paper is clearly written, and the proposed solution raises relevant questions in relation to the theme "Transparency and inclusivity of the assessment processes".

It would be helpful to clarify whether the script will be openly shared and made reusable by others. Given that Scopus citation data is not openly accessible and tends to prioritize English-language journal articles, it would be interesting to know how easily the process and script could be adapted to use a more inclusive and transparent data source, such as OpenAlex?

Finally, while citation counts are a useful complement to metrics like downloads, page views, and links for assessing data reuse, I particularly appreciate the idea of analyzing citations to gain insights into user communities and how they engage with the data. I hope this interpretive aspect is given sufficient attention in the poster.

I recommend this poster for acceptance.

Feedback Reviewer 2 Clifford Tatum

	Reviewer 2				
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID11	5	3	4	3	Borderline

Relevance to Conference Themes and Topics

This proposal aligns well with the conference's overarching themes, particularly the focus on open infrastructures for responsible research assessment. The work addresses a concrete technical challenge, tracking data reuse' and offers an open, replicable method that can strengthen transparency in assessing research impact.

Significance

The ability to reliably track data reuse is an important problem for research infrastructures, funders, and individual researchers. By moving beyond less reliable measures such as downloads or page views, the proposed method has the potential to improve the evaluation of open datasets. However, it's unclear how the approach addresses "inaccurate citation practices among scholars". The method's reach ultimately depends on researchers following good citation practices, meaning it seems to capture accurate, visible reuse rather than all reuse.

Novelty and Originality

The proposal offers a practical tool in the form of an R script that operationalizes dataset citation tracking by linking DOIs to Scopus data. Its emphasis on bibliographic reference analysis addresses both technical and operational limitations found in existing approaches. In the context of the conference theme, it raises the question of whether the approach is compatible also with open research information. The contribution is directly applicable to CESSDA archives and appears adaptable to other research information repositories.

Clarity and Quality of Presentation

The proposal is generally clear and logically structured, with relevant references to prior work. The description of the problem, context, and proposed solution is clear, though at times it reads as densely technical, which may limit accessibility for a broader audience. For the conference presentation, the work could be strengthened by illustrating the method with concrete examples of tracked data reuse, showing the kinds of insights the tool can generate, and clarifying how these outputs could connect to broader assessment frameworks discussed at the event.